

IMPROVING THE TECHNIQUE OF OBTAINING A FUNCTIONAL IMPRESSION FROM THE LOWER JAW

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Abstract

The functional design of the boundaries of the prosthesis behind the molar area provides for the base to cover the mucous membrane of the alveolar tubercle, without displacement by the impression material. In the lateral areas, the base of the prosthesis should ensure free movement of the mylohyoid muscle. In the area of the retro-maxillary-hyoid line, the functional state of the hyoglossus muscle should be taken into account.

Keywords: edentulous lower jaw, prosthetic bed, functional impressions, orthopedic treatment.

The choice of a rational technique for obtaining a functional impression is the most important condition for the effectiveness of orthopedic treatment for complete tooth loss [2]. Using one or another impression material, designing impression trays in different ways, taking impressions under greater or less pressure, the authors pursued one goal: creating a prosthesis of a certain shape [3]. Purpose of the study: Assessing the quality of prosthetics for the edentulous lower jaw under unfavorable anatomical and topographic conditions by improving functional impressions.

Material and methods

Orthopedic treatment was carried out in 28 patients (16 men and 12 women) aged from 56 to 74 years with various degrees of atrophy of the alveolar process of the edentulous lower jaw, including 5 with II degree, 13 with III degree, 10 with IV degree. The degree of atrophy was determined according to the Köhler classification [1]. The dentures were manufactured using generally accepted technology with an anatomical impression taken from the lower jaw using alginate impression materials. Using plaster models, after determining the boundaries, we began to directly manufacture an individual tray from a standard plate of light-curing polymer from Megadenta. The plate was crimped according to the model and polymerized in a special stationary Megalight MINI box for five minutes. After removing the individual spoon from the model, the sharp edges were processed. Then we began to fit an individual spoon, taking into account the functional state of the muscles of the floor of the mouth, and conducting functional tests. The edge of the spoon overlaps the oblique and mylohyoid line by 1-1.5 mm. The spoon was again placed in the oral cavity, and functional tests were performed with moderate movements of the lower jaw and tongue. The volume of the transitional fold was determined using thermoplastic or silicone impression materials. We achieved fixation of an individual tray on the jaw at rest and during functional diagnostic tests. The final functional impression was obtained using silicone impression materials. As the impression materials hardened, the edges of the impression were formed using tongue movements. Moving the tongue forward

until it touches the incisive papilla allows you to fix the frenulum of the tongue in the anterior position. To fix the area of the retromaxillary-hyoid muscle in a functional state, the patient was offered 3-4 swallowing movements with an interval of 10-15 seconds. The finished impression was removed from the oral cavity, a plaster model was cast on it, and a complete removable laminar denture was made from acrylic plastic using the generally accepted method.

Results and discussion

To evaluate the results obtained, we analyzed the functional effectiveness of orthopedic treatment in patients with unfavorable anatomical and topographic conditions of the prosthetic bed on the edentulous lower jaw. In 18 (64.2%) patients with atrophy of the alveolar part of the lower jaw, stability of the dentures was observed during chewing, wide mouth opening, loud speech, and tongue protrusion. Of these, 5 (27.7%) were with degree II atrophy, 8 (44.4%) with degree III and 5 (27.7%) with degree IV. In 7 (26%) patients, the dentures were stable during chewing, normal mouth opening, and normal speech. Of these, 4 (57.14%) patients had grade III atrophy, 3 (17.6%) had grade IV. In 2 (7.1%) patients, the stability of the dentures was recorded when chewing non-solid food, normal mouth opening, and normal speech. Of these, 1 (50%) with grade III atrophy, 1 (50%) with grade IV atrophy. In 1 (3.7%) patient with IV degree of atrophy, poor stability of the dentures was noted during chewing, normal mouth opening, and normal speech. This patient, after studying the reasons for unsatisfactory results, underwent repeated prosthetics. Conclusions 1. To achieve optimal fixation of dentures on the edentulous lower jaw, it is necessary to functionally design the space of the vestibule of the oral cavity, which should be used to expand the boundaries of the denture base to a large extent in case of IV degree of atrophy of the alveolar part, to a lesser extent in its II degree. A positive effect is observed when the base is expanded taking into account the anatomical and topographical features of the edentulous lower jaw.

2. It is more expedient to carry out the functional design of the boundaries of the prostheses in the buccal

area by overlapping the oblique line by 1-1.5 mm. The alveolar ridge on the lingual side in most patients is covered with a poorly pliable mucous membrane, reaching the border with the floor of the oral cavity. In this area, the mucous membrane of the floor of the mouth in some cases forms a folded elevation. A gap is formed between the base of the alveolar process and the fold of the mucous membrane, which can help to obtain a closing valve in this area.

3. The functional design of the boundaries of the prosthesis behind the molar area provides for the base to cover the mucous membrane of the alveolar tubercle, without displacement by the impression material. In the lateral areas, the base of the prosthesis should ensure free movement of the mylohyoid muscle. In the area of the retromaxillary-hyoid line, the functional state of the hyoglossus muscle should be taken into account.

Conclusion.

Thus, our clinical observations allow the proposed method of obtaining functional impressions of the edentulous lower jaw to be recommended for use in an orthopedic dentistry clinic.

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